

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

PREVALENT SKIN DISEASES IN ELDERLY DERMATOLOGY PATIENTS: A RETROSPECTIVE ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Background: The documentation of the spectrum of skin diseases in individuals aged 60 years and over is not readily done despite older individuals accounting for a large percentage of dermatology patients. The study aimed to document the spectrum of skin diseases diagnosed in dermatology patients aged 60 years and over, and to conduct a gender based comparison of diagnoses.

Methodology: This was a retrospective cross-sectional study of 482 patients aged 60 years and over who attended the outpatient dermatology clinic of the Lagos State University Teaching Hospital, between January 2017 and December 2022. Sociodemographic data: age, gender and diagnoses were documented. Diagnoses were coded using the ICD-10 code. Clinical diagnoses were compared between males and females. Data was analyzed using SPSS version 25. Frequency and means are presented. Chi-squared, Fischers' exact test and the Student 't' test were utilized for comparisons and significance. A p-value <0.05 was considered significant for all statistical tests.

Results: Patients aged 60 years and above accounted for 14.4% of the dermatology patients. The population was 43% male with a mean age (\pm SD) of 38.6 (17.5) and an age range of 60 to 98 years. Non-infectious diseases accounted for 71% of the diagnoses, followed by infectious diseases at 14.9% and tumours at 14.1%. The commonest group of diseases diagnosed were the eczemas and dermatitis (26.8%), papulosquamous diseases (8.5%) and fungal infections (7.7%). On comparison of diagnosis between males and females, autoimmune connective tissue diseases was more in females ($p=0.0219$) while urticaria and angioedema ($p=0.0379$) were significantly more diagnosed in men.

Conclusions: Eczemas and dermatitis followed by fungal infections are the commonest skin diseases in older individuals. Tumours are mostly benign and include seborrheic dermatosis and keloid. Gender based differences include autoimmune connective tissue diseases in women and, urticaria and angioedema in men. Health planning should take into cognizance these diseases for effective and appropriate care of the elderly.

Keywords: Elderly, Skin disease, Clinical profile, Prevalence, Dermatitis, Eczemas

Introduction

Life expectancy has increased globally and the care of the older individual has become relevant. In addition to other medical concerns, skin diseases also occur in the older individuals.¹⁻³ However, specific documentation of the spectrum of skin disease in this group of individuals is not routinely done despite individuals sixty years and

older accounting for 10.7 to 80% of dermatology clinic patients.^{4,5}

In the few studies where skin diseases in older individuals have been reported, fungal and viral infections, eczemas (hand and foot diseases), pruritus, papulosquamous diseases and benign skin tumours were the commonest diseases.^{1,3,5-7} Yew et al in a 15-year study of the burden of skin

diseases among the elderly in Singapore reported dermatitis, viral skin diseases, fungal skin diseases, psoriasis and keratinocyte carcinoma as the top five most common skin conditions.⁴ Dry skin is frequently reported and this occurs in 4.7 to 60% of this age group.^{1,6-8} Hand eczema although occurring in only 2.7% is reported to be discomforting.⁹ In a study of the prevalence of skin tumours in 2038 elderly patients in China, 3.8% of them were found to have skin tumours.¹⁰ The tumours were mostly seborrheic keratosis, actinic keratosis, squamous and basal cell carcinomas.¹⁰

A PubMed search does not reveal a specific documentation of the spectrum of skin diseases in the older individuals in dermatology clinics in Nigeria. A documentation of the skin diseases in this aged group is important in health planning consequent upon the increasing life expectancy and in the appropriate treatment of this age group. This study aimed to document the spectrum of skin diseases diagnosed in dermatology patients aged 60 years and over. In addition, we sought to conduct a gender based comparison of diagnoses.

Materials and Methods

This retrospective cross-sectional study was conducted on 482 patients aged 60 years and over who attended the outpatient dermatology clinic of the Lagos State University Teaching Hospital, between January 2017 and December 2022. Ethical approval for the study was given by the ethics review board of the hospital, (LREC/10/06/1209). Case records were retrieved and relevant information: age, gender, duration of complaint and diagnosis was documented. Diagnosis was mostly clinical but when necessary, skin biopsies, bacteriological analysis and nail scrapings for mycology were performed. Only the first clinical diagnosis was utilized in the study irrespective of the number of diagnoses. Clinical diagnoses were compared between males and females.

Data Analysis

Data was analyzed using the IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences, version 25. Using the ICD-10 code, all skin diseases were broadly categorized into infective, non-infective and tumour. All skin diseases were categorized into eight major disease categories as closely as possible. The ninth category (“other disorders of

the skin and subcutaneous tissue”) was further classified into five subgroups. The frequency of each skin diagnosis and the group was determined. Age and gender distribution of the major skin disease categories was done. Chi-squared and Fishers’ exact tests were used to determine the association between the broad skin disease classification (infective, non-infective and tumors) with gender. Student ‘t’ test was used to compare the diagnoses of the males and females. A p-value <0.05 was considered significant for all statistical test.

Results

Patients aged 60 years and above accounted for 14.4% (482/3354) of the patients who attended the clinic for the first time over the seven-year period. The population was 43% male and the M : F was 1:1. The mean age (\pm SD) of the patients was 38.6 (17.5) and the age range was 60 to 98 years. Table 1

Non-infectious diseases accounted for 71% of the diagnoses and this was followed by infectious diseases at 14.9% and tumours at 14.1%. The commonest group of diseases diagnosed were the eczemas and dermatitis, papulosquamous diseases and fungal infections. While lipomas, radiation-related disorders of the skin and lymphomas were rare, no neural tumours were diagnosed. Table 2 The percentages of the ten commonest diseases are as shown in figure 1. The eczemas and dermatitis accounted for the commonest diseases necessitating clinic attendance followed by papulosquamous diseases. Connective tissue diseases although part of the ten common diseases were relatively uncommon.

On comparison of diagnosis between males and females, autoimmune connective tissue diseases, urticaria and angioedema were significantly more diagnosed in women. Table 3

Discussion

This study documents the spectrum of skin diseases diagnosed in adults aged 60 years and over. It in addition, highlights gender based differences in diagnoses. The commonest group of diseases diagnosed were the eczemas and dermatitis followed by fungal infections. Lipoma was the least diagnosed disease. Gender based comparison of skin diseases diagnosed, revealed

autoimmune connective tissue diseases in women;
urticaria and angioedema in men.

Table 1. Age sex distribution of the patients

Variable	Male (n = 205)	Female (n = 277)	Total (n = 482)
Age (mean,sd)	69.9 (8.2)	69.4 (7.7)	69.6 (7.9)
Age range	60 - 97	60 - 98	60 - 98
Age group (years) (n, %)			
60-64	65 (31.7)	84 (30.3)	149 (30.9)
65 - 69	50 (24.4)	82 (29.6)	132 (27.4)
70 - 74	41 (20.0)	48 (17.3)	89 (18.5)
75 - 79	23 (11.2)	27 (9.7)	50 (10.4)
>80	26 (12.7)	36 (13.0)	62 (12.9)

Table 2. Distribution of dermatological diseases

Dermatologica disease	Male n = 205 (%)	Females n = 277 (%)	Total n = 482
Non-infectious skin diseases			
1. Dermatitis and eczema	63 (30.7)	66 (23.8)	129 (26.8)
2. Urticaria and angioedema	13 (6.3)	7 (2.5)	20 (4.2)
3. Papulosquamous	17 (8.3)	24 (8.7)	41 (8.5)
4. Bullous dermatoses	5 (2.4)	6 (2.2)	11 (2.3)
5. Disorders of skin appendages	5 (2.4)	6 (2.2)	11 (2.3)
6. Radiation-related disorders of the skin	1 (.5)	2 (0.7)	3 (0.6)
7. Other disorders of the skin and subcutaneous tissue			
A. Pigmentary disorders	10 (4.9)	19 (6.9)	29 (6.0)
B. Scaling and cornified diseases	7 (3.4)	6 (2.2)	13 (2.7)
C. Autoimmune connective tissue disorders	1 (0.5)	12 (4.3)	13 (2.7)
D. Adverse reaction to drugs	1 (0.5)	3 (1.1)	4 (0.8)
E. Others	17 (8.3)	31 (11.2)	48 (9.9)
8. Infectious Skin diseases			
Fungal infection of the skin	13 (6.3)	24 (8.7)	37 (7.7)
Viral infection of the skin	12 (5.9)	13 (4.7)	25 (5.2)
Bacterial infection of the skin	2 (1.0)	3 (1.1)	5 (1.0)
Parasitic infection of the skin	4 (2.0)	1 (0.4)	5 (1.0)
9. Tumours, pre-malignant and malignant lesions			
Epidermal tumours	7 (3.4)	13 (4.7)	20 (4.2)
Neural tumours	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Melanocytic tumours	2 (1.0)	2 (0.7)	4 (0.8)
Vascular tumours	3 (1.5)	2 (0.7)	5 (1.0)
Adnexial tumours	3 (1.5)	6 (2.2)	9 (1.9)
Keloid	10 (4.9)	16 (5.8)	26 (5.4)
Lymphomas	2 (1.0)	1 (0.4)	3 (0.6)
Lipomas	0 (0.0)	1 (0.4)	1 (0.2)

Table 3. Comparison of distribution of dermatological diseases between males and females

Dermatologica disease	Male n = 205 (%)	Females n = 277 (%)	p
Non-infectious skin diseases			
1. Dermatitis and eczema	63 (30.7)	66 (23.8)	0.0904
2. Urticaria and angioedema	13 (6.3)	7 (2.5)	0.0379
3. Papulosquamous	17 (8.3)	24 (8.7)	0.8851
4. Bullous dermatoses	5 (2.4)	6 (2.2)	1.000*
5. Disorders of skin appendages	5 (2.4)	6 (2.2)	1.000*
6. Radiation-related disorders of the skin	1 (0.5)	2 (0.7)	1.000*
7. Other disorders of the skin and subcutaneous tissue			
A. Pigmentary disorders	10 (4.9)	19 (6.9)	0.3658
B. Scaling and cornified diseases	7 (3.4)	6 (2.2)	0.5808
C. Autoimmune connective tissue disorders	1 (0.5)	12 (4.3)	0.0219*
D. Adverse reaction to drugs	1 (0.5)	3 (1.1)	0.8381*
E. Others	17 (8.3)	31 (11.2)	0.2934
8. Infectious Skin diseases			
A. Fungal infection of the skin	13 (6.3)	24 (8.7)	0.3436
B. Viral infection of the skin	12 (5.9)	13 (4.7)	0.5700
C. Bacterial infection of the skin	2 (1.0)	3 (1.1)	1.000*
D. Parasitic infection of the skin	4 (2.0)	1 (0.4)	0.2117*
9. Tumours, pre-malignant and malignant lesions			
A. Epidermal tumours	7 (3.4)	13 (4.7)	0.4865
B. Neural tumours	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	-
C. Melanocytic tumours	2 (1.0)	2 (0.7)	1.000*
D. Vascular tumours	3 (1.5)	2 (0.7)	0.7342*
E. Adnexial tumours	3 (1.5)	6 (2.2)	0.8234*
F. Keloid	10 (4.9)	16 (5.8)	0.6660
G. Lymphomas	2 (1.0)	1 (0.4)	1.000*
H. Lipomas	0 (0.0)	1 (0.4)	1.000*

*Fischer's exact P-value

Figure 1. Pie chart showing the ten commonest diseases diagnosed in percentages

Although slightly more females attended the clinic, the male female ratio was one to one. In addition, there was no significant difference in age range and the proportion of patients in the various age groups between the genders. Our study is in consonance with other studies of skin disease in the elderly of a female preponderance.^{1,3,4}

Non-infectious diseases

The commonest group of diseases diagnosed were non-infectious. The low frequency of infectious diseases is accounted for by the age group studied. This age group is no longer the working class group thus reducing their exposure to sources of cutaneous infections like farming. Inflammatory diseases, specifically the eczemas and dermatitis followed by papulosquamous were the main reason for clinic attendance. The reason for the high frequency of these group of diseases is due to the tendency for these diseases to be pruritic, unsightly, uncomfortable and located in exposed anatomical parts. Similar to our study, eczemas and dermatitis are the most frequent group of diseases diagnosed in this age group by other authors.^{2-5,7} Radiation related disorders were rare. We attribute this to the protective effect of melanin in this race and decreased out-door activities due to age. There was no specific mention of radiation-related disorders in other studies making comparison difficult.^{1,3,4} In addition connective tissue diseases were uncommon. This we attribute to the age of the patients studied as connective tissue diseases occur more in child bearing young females.¹¹

Neoplastic diseases

Tumours were not frequent in this study and this is in keeping with cutaneous tumours being infrequent in Africans.^{10,12-14} Of the tumoural diseases, keloids followed by epidermal tumours were the commonly diagnosed ones. Lymphomas and lipomas were rare. Keloids occur commonly in Africans, has an onset in middle age and are persistent.^{15,16} Their occurrence in this study is thus not surprising. Epidermal tumours which were mostly seborrheic keratosis and dermatosis papulose nigras were the next common tumours. These are tumours commonly associated with aging, richly pigmented skin and sun exposure: factors present in our patients.¹⁰ Huang et al in a similar study found a low frequency of tumours in

richly pigmented individuals and in the few who had them, it was seborrheic keratosis similar to our finding.¹⁰ Neural tumours were not found in the patients. The common neural tumours are neurofibromas and schwannomas. From literature, these tumours have a low frequency of occurrence in the population studied.^{12,14} Although, we are unable to explain their complete absence, our study finding is similar that in other studies of skin diseases in the elderly.^{1,4,10}

Infectious diseases

Infectious diseases had a low occurrence in the patients. We attribute this to the age of the patients. At this age, most of the patients are pensioners with decreased exposure to occupations like farming which would expose them to sources of infections. In those who had infections, fungal followed by viral infections were the commonest infections diagnosed. Fungal diseases were mostly onychomycosis and tinea pedis. Viral infections were mainly warts and herpes zoster. Aging comes with the burden of non-communicable diseases like diabetes mellitus with increased susceptibility to cutaneous infections.^{17,18} In addition, the aging process itself reduces the immune surveillance capacity of the skin with a resultant increase in susceptibility to cutaneous infections. Furthermore, at this age most individuals are on medications for various diseases which could increase their susceptibility to infections. Following similar studies of skin disease in the elderly, a similar occurrence of fungal and viral diseases is reported.¹⁻³

Bacterial infections were rare. This could be due to the common practice of self-medication¹⁹ or a true reflection of the documented decrease in bacterial infections consequent on improved hygienic processes.^{14,20} Similar studies of skin diseases reported a low occurrence of bacterial diseases in the elderly.^{1,2}

Comparison of diseases based on gender

When skin disease occurrence was compared between males and females, autoimmune connective tissue diseases was significantly more diagnosed in women. Urticaria and angioedema was significantly more diagnosed in men. In addition, although not attaining to statistical significance, papulosquamous diseases, pigmentary disorders, fungal infections and

keloids were diagnosed more in females. There was equal frequency of cutaneous viral infection diagnosis. Similar to our study, other authors have reported a gender based difference in skin disease occurrence. These differences are in both the type of diseases diagnosed and the gender affected. Drewitz et al found hand eczema to be more in males.⁹ Sarac et al found fungal infections more in males.¹ Kandwal et al reported fungal infections, eczema and psoriasis more in males.² Studies on dry skin are inconclusive as Mekic et al found it to affect females more and Kandwal et al found it to affect males more.^{2,8} These studies did not report the season of study nor the moisturizing behavior of the patients: factors which contribute to how dry the skin can be. In contrast to other studies, we did not find any gender based difference in tumour occurrence.^{1,10,21} In these studies, tumours occurred more in males. Our study had a low level of tumour occurrence. We are unsure if this contributed to this lack of a difference in tumour occurrence

Conclusion

Our study is limited by the number of patients studied and the retrospective nature of the study with the attendant inability to explore the diagnosed diseases in detail. In conclusion, skin diseases occur in the elderly. Eczemas and dermatitis followed by fungal infections are the commonest diagnoses. Tumours are mostly benign and include seborrheic dermatosis and keloid. Lymphomas and lipomas are rare. There are gender based differences in skin disease with autoimmune connective tissue diseases being diagnosed more in women and, urticaria and angioedema in men. Health planning should take into cognizance these diseases for effective and appropriate care of the elderly..

Declarations

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Conflicts of Interest/Competing Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Code availability

Data is available on request.

Authors' Contributions

ELA: Conceptualization, literature review, patient evaluation, write up and manuscript review; **OMC:** Conceptualization, patient

evaluation, write up and manuscript review; **OA:** Conceptualization, patient evaluation, write up and manuscript review; **OA:** Conceptualization, patient evaluation, write up and manuscript review; **OO:** Conceptualization, patient evaluation, write up and manuscript review.

Ethics approval

Ethical approval for the study was given by the ethics review board of the hospital, (LREC/10/06/1209).

Consent to participate

Not applicable.

Consent for publication

Not required.

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